

IMPACT OF SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS ON THE PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT OF ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract

Children born and live not only in a society but also in a specific part of it. This paper identifies major socio-cultural factors affecting child's personality development and different recommendation are proposed, focusing on parents reason ability toward children education, governments role in providing quality education to all school children.

INTRODUCTION

The term personality connotes, physical attractiveness, charm good nature, case of manner, "outgoingness" or any other form of behaviour or attitude that induces a favourable impression. Even word or phrase that indicates a way, in which an individual acts at a given situation, is a description of one aspect of personality. Personality is the "quality of individuals habits thought and expression, his attitudes and interest, his manner of acting and his personal philosophy of life (Woodworth, 1997).

Personality is the individual's relatively distinct and consistent manner of perceiving, thinking, feeling and behaving. This pattern of existence is some times used to infer the fundamental essence of the individual functioning in the physical, psychological, and social worlds (international Encyclopedia of sociology, 1995).

The development of personality is conceived primarily as a process of learning which arises when the infant's innate behavior repertoire is exposed to environmental circumstances. Personality and character develop chiefly during the impressive years. Everyone is born with heredity and potential that is shaped and molded by surroundings or culture. Heredity and environment both play a major part in the development of a person's total personality. Attitudes, habits and interest as well as character and conscience including the morals as spiritual ideas, standards, life's values and mode of social expression are all integral parts of personality (Harris, 1995)

The aspects of the existence of an individual are numerous, most of which are genetically determined and in the majority of cases, environment has a critical role in the completion of what nature has started. Personality and its changes over life span are a good example of such a phenomenon. Personality is defined as the distinguishing characteristics of an individual which differentiate him/her from others when displayed in a wide variety of situations and circumstances especially social ones (Connell, 1985). In fact, the development of personality which is the outcome of the interaction between genetic make-up of an individual and his environment, starts parentally or even before conception since genetics has something to do with it. In children, personality has a considerable potential for growth and changes i.e. very flexible, but it is rigid i.e. unalterable in adults. Personality and its development are under the influence of some determinants.

Nurture as biological development and rearing of a child. That is genetic as the determining factor in child growth and upbringing. The importance of inheritance in the determination of individual differences in physiognomy and physique has seldom been seriously questioned. But there has been much less certainty about the degree to which individual differences in social behavior and intelligence might also be generally determined. Genetic variables contribute significantly to the development of intelligence and social behavior.

Nature refers to all other factors that affect the growth of the child. Nature could also be seen in terms of all extended factors that surround and enhance human growth and development apart from heredity or biological factors. This includes food, rest, exercise, personal hygiene, among others. To grow big and strong and to be healthy, the child has to have good balance diet food from the time he is born. Environment is considered the major extrinsic one (Richardson, 1990.). Cultural, racial, socioeconomic, educational, social guidance and health conditions could be environmental factors playing a critical role in personality development.

(Atkinson, 1996). Parental education, health and emotional states, social interactions are other factors which influence personality development. Several theories were stated explaining the development of personality, each of which dealt with the concept personality development from a different point of view.

The Learning theory is another theory of personality development that is concerned mainly with child and his social background and which rose the idea that behavior is modified by experience (Theodore, 1983). The psychoanalytic development theory was modified by Erik Erikson and Stack Sullivan. The later emphasized the importance of interpersonal transactions between parents and child and the child's development in a. Erikson formulated eight stages development focusing upon the specific develop mental tasks of each phase (psychosocial crisis). Generally, the life cycle is divided into eight developmental stages. These stages were: infancy, toddlerhood, Preschool child, school child adolescence young adulthood, middle years and old age...

The adolescence stage of growth and development, which represent the industry vs role confusion stage of the psychosocial theory of development, occur from 12 to 20 years of age (Theodore, 1983). Adolescence is a transitional stage between childhood and adult life and is characterized by rapid physical growth and psychological, mental and social maturity (Peter, 1993). This stage of development officially begins at puberty and ends with person achieving a level of maturity enough to deal with and manage realities of life and be able to bear responsibility of him/her self and his/her actions. The developmental tasks faced by the child at this age are accepting changes in the body and appearance, developing appropriate relationships with males and females role of the same age, accepting the male and female role appropriate for one's age, becoming independent from parents and adults, developing morals, attitudes, and values needed for functioning in society

The child usually identifies himself/herself with numbers of his/her family in an all-or-none fashion. He/she interiorize in similar fashion many of the standards which the family as a group upholds. He/she is "all for" some features of the family situation and those who belong to familiar relations. On the other hand, he/she is "dead set" against other aspects of what goes on in the family and some of the characteristics of members of the family. The child's philosophy is a kind of absolutism which makes over his/her world into black and white, good people and bad people. Many parents fail to train their children in that independent and responsible action which the latter need if they are to assume easily their adult roles during adolescence.

One of the most interesting and fruitful developments in adolescence psychology in recent years has been the growing research on the relations of the adolescent to his contemporaries. In their socio psychological study of the ego, have emphasized the importance of the age mate groups to which the adolescent relates himself. This "self imposed isolation" from adults in which the adolescent cares little or nothing for the approval or disapproval of adults (save where it may serve his own ends), sometimes leads to apologetic explanations to his peers about the "meddling" of his parents in the group's affairs.

He distinguishes three such systems of social rank in society, each of those of the (1) Social classes and (2) the ethnic or foreign born groups, both of which are less sharply stratified (3) the color castes. It is possible at presents for a child born into a social class or an ethnic group having low status to move into a higher status and a higher cultural level by learning the necessary behavior and displaying the necessary

- The study of child development helps therapists and educators to better assist those with special needs, such as those with emotional or learning difficulties.
- Understanding child development contributes to self understanding. We know ourselves better by recognizing the influences that have made us into the people we are today.

Major Socio cultural factors affecting upon child's personality development

The following are major socio cultural factors affecting upon child's personality development

Parents

A great deal of socialization that takes place in the family is deliberate, but much of it is quite unconscious. The patterns of social interaction with in the family may provide unintended models for the latter behaviour and personality traits of the children when they grow to adulthood.

Vandell (2000) He claimed that I have constructed a "straw man" that I have accused developmentalists of holding a view of development that has been dead for years. But "this view of the child as a blank slate on which parents are free to create". Bisin and Verder (1998) studied the formation of preferences of social status' as the result of intergeneration transmission of cultural traits.

Maccoby (1983) wrote that the contribution of parental practices to children's personality cannot be viewed in isolation. Each parental behaviour or parental

personality trait is part of a complex system that in some respects is unique to each parent child relationship.

Family members

The family is without doubt the most significant single agent of socialization in the societies. One reason for the important of the family is that it has the main responsibility for socializing children in the crucial early year of life. The family is where children establish their first close emotional ties, learn language, and begin to internalize cultural norms and values. To young children the family is all encompassing. They have little social experience beyond it boundaries and therefore lack any basis for comparing and evaluating what is learned from family members. Each family therefore offers a unique experience to the children within it.

Siblings

Abramovitch et al. (1986) expressed that though at first glance it seems counterintuitive that children fail to apply what they learned in their sibling relationships to their relationships with peers the tendency not to generalize it adaptive children who are dominated by older siblings at home would be handicapped, not helped by the expectation that they also be dominated by their peer. Infact, even in every childhood, later born children are no more likely than firstborns to adopts a submissive in peer interaction. Finally, the qualities of siblings relationships affect social competence as well. Stocker et al (1990) found that personality traits that had a positive effect on relationship quality was a shy older sibling, a sociable younger sibling, a low frequency of upset in both the older and you younger sibling, and a short duration of upset for the younger sibling.

Non-family relationships

Hamre and Planta (2001) revealed that it is very possible that an individual other than the parent could contribute to a youth's development of social competence. Throughout many children's lives non-related adults, such as teacher, "fictive" aunts and uncles, foster grand parents, coaches, neighbors, and mentors, figure strongly in their social circle and development. In fact, encouragement, physical and emotional affection warmth, skill modeling and an environment in which children felt comfortable to test, and develop trust in, social relationships.

Peer relationships

As children grow older, they spend more and more time in the company of their peers people of roughly equivalent age and other social characteristics. Within peer group, the young are able for the first time to choose their own companions and to interact with others on the basis of equality. However, they cannot expect the automatic acceptance from the peers that they can from family members and so have to learn to present the self in the way that win the approval of the group.

Neighborhood

It comprises upon the surrounding habitat of the children. The neighborhood is usually the first outsider with which the children interact, even before going to school sometimes the community influence determines the other agents of socialization like selection of schools, peers or clubs.

Schooling

The school is an agent formally charged by the task of socializing the young in particular skills and values. In this setting the young one's come from the first time under the direct supervision of people who are not relatives. The individual child is no longer considered somebody special; he or she is one of the crowd, subject to same regulation and expectations that everyone else is subjected to Participation in the life of school also lessen the dependence on the family creates new links to the wider society beyond . The immediate task of the schools is to socialize the youngs ones in cognitive skills such as reading or mathematics and to provide knowledge about a variety of subjects such as history or chemistry, that may not be available in the home.

Extracurricular Involvement

Clubs and other recreational society memberships provide an opportunity to children to independently intermingle and socialize themselves with other people of different ages and also of the same peer group. Clubs provide kids not only a source to participate in the physical activities and prove their physical fitness but also a platform to interact with their peers and other to discuss different academic opportunities and select their career field to determine their future path of independent life.

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CONCLUSION

“Children are our future and we try to know what their requirement at different stages of life are, in order to bring them before main stream of life”. The adolescent stage occurs from 12 to 21 years of age it is a transition stage between childhood and adult life and is characterized by rapid physical growing psychological, mental and social maturity. It is the stage when adult body features and personality trait begin to developed.

The study of adolescent's personality develop is important for parents, teachers, society and all those who have relation in nurturing good youth for eliminating obstacles for healthy brain development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Education plays a very vital role in personality development. It is usually said that knowledge creates a difference between a human being and animals. Therefore, the more knowledgeable and educated the society is, the better will be the personality development of children. So it is very important for parents to give due consideration and importance to their children education.
- However, achievement of educated society objective cannot be achieved without the interference of government. Simple development of government school is not the solution of this problem. It's the quality of education that counts in the long run.
- Socialization of children is also an important factor, which needs to give due consideration by parents. Therefore, parents have to keep a good eye on children's friends and the company they keep out at the same time should arrange parties of their children friends.
- Schools can provide parents with information about child rearing skill: the importance of family support, child and adolescent development.
- Effective communication with families about school programs and their child's progress is visible. This involves both school to-home and home to school communication. School times for parent meetings that are convenient for them to attend.
- Another way of making a school family friendly is to crease a parent room or parent another at the school. There parents can help each others, help the school and receive information or assistance from the school or community.

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